

ІННОВАЦІЙНО- ІНВЕСТИЦІЙНА ПОЛІТИКА

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Architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization

The subject of the research is theoretical strategic approaches to ensuring the competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization.

The aim of the research is to determine the theoretical foundations of the architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization.

Research methods. The main methods were method of system analysis; induction and deduction; literature search method; competitive analysis; strategic analysis, factor analysis; graphical and others.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that the architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization is gaining relevance in the context of dynamic changes in the world economic space, increasing competition in the global market and the importance of innovation for ensuring the sustainable development of companies. It is determined that enterprises must quickly adapt to the challenges of globalization, in particular through the introduction of innovative strategies and new technologies, where innovation is becoming a key factor determining the ability of companies not only to maintain their market position but also to expand their capabilities in the international arena. It is proved that modern enterprises are facing such global trends as digitalization, environmental transformation, and integration into international logistics, which requires an effective competitiveness management strategy. The study of competitiveness architectonics allows us to reveal the structural elements and interrelationships that form a comprehensive system of competitive advantages of innovation-oriented enterprises. Given the constant changes in the global market, it is important to understand how globalization processes affect the development of innovative enterprises and what strategies can ensure their sustainability and success in the long term. It is determined that the architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises is a system of structural and functional components that provide the enterprise with a stable position in the market in the context of the following potentials: innovation potential; financial potential; marketing potential; organizational potential. The main factors of influence on innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of globalization are investigated: access to international markets; international cooperation; technology transfer; competitive pressure. The strategic directions of innovation-oriented enterprises to improve competitiveness in the context

of globalization are proposed: investing in innovation; improving the efficiency of operations; global presence; international cooperation.

Scope of the results. Competitiveness of the enterprise, enterprise economics, enterprise strategy, enterprise management, enterprise innovation, enterprise efficiency, international and global economy.

Conclusions. As a result, we have proved that the competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon that requires an effective management architecture. It is established that enterprises that are able to adapt to new challenges, using innovation as the basis of their strategy and actively developing their international presence, have a better chance of operating effectively. It has been determined that in the context of globalization, competitiveness is not limited to local markets – it has an international dimension, which requires a strategic approach to managing innovations and resources. It is established that the intensive growth of globalization has affected the dynamics of development of many sectors of the economy, especially in the context of the spread of information technology and rapid innovation. It is proved that innovative enterprises seeking to be competitive in the international arena must constantly adapt to changes and develop new technological solutions: the competitiveness of such enterprises largely depends on their ability to innovate, adapt strategies to global conditions and respond quickly to new challenges. The author proposes to define competitiveness architectonics as a set of interrelated components that allow an enterprise to maintain and strengthen its position in international markets, where innovative strategies, flexibility and openness to change are the basis for successful functioning in the context of global competition.

Keywords: architectonics, competitiveness, innovations, enterprises, international globalization, world space, enterprise development, strategies, integration, transformation, potential, factors of influence.

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Архітектоніка конкурентоспроможності інноваційно-орієнтованих підприємств в контексті міжнародної глобалізації

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні стратегічні підходи щодо забезпечення конкурентоспроможності інноваційно-орієнтованих підприємств в контексті міжнародної глобалізації

Метою дослідження є визначення теоретичних основ архітектоніки конкурентоспроможності інноваційно-орієнтованих підприємств в контексті міжнародної глобалізації.

Методи дослідження. Основними методами стали: метод системного аналізу; індукції та дедукції; літературно-пошуковий метод; конкурентний аналіз; стратегічний аналіз, факторний аналіз; графічний та інші.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, архітектоніка конкурентоспроможності інноваційно-орієнтованих підприємств у контексті міжнародної глобалізації набуває актуальності в контексті динамічних змін світового економічного простору, підвищення рівня конкуренції на глобальному ринку та важливості інновацій для забезпечення стабільного розвитку компаній. Визначено, що підприємства повинні оперативнo адаптуватися до викликів глобалізації, зокрема через впровадження інноваційних стратегій та нових технологій, де інновації стають ключовим чинником, що визначає здатність компаній не лише втримати позиції на ринку, але й розширювати свої можливості на міжнародній арені. Доведено, що сучасні підприємства стикаються з такими глобальними трендами, як цифровізація, екологічна трансформація, інтеграція в міжнародну логістику, що вимагає ефективної стратегії управління конкурентоспроможністю. Дослідження архітектоніки конкурентоспроможності дозволяє розкрити структурні елементи та взаємозв'язки, які формують комплексну систему конкурентних переваг інноваційно-орієнтованих підприємств. Враховуючи постійні зміни на світовому ринку, важливо зрозуміти, як глобалізаційні процеси впливають на розвиток інноваційних підприємств, та які стратегії можуть забезпечити їхню стійкість і успішність у довгостроковій перспективі. Визначено, що архітектоніка конкурентоспроможності інноваційно-орієн-

тованих підприємств – це система структурних і функціональних компонентів, які забезпечують підприємству стійкі позиції на ринку в контексті таких потенціалів: інноваційний потенціал; фінансовий потенціал; маркетинговий потенціал; організаційний потенціал. Досліджено основні чинники впливу на інноваційно-орієнтовані підприємства в умовах глобалізації: доступ до міжнародних ринків; міжнародна кооперація; трансфер технологій; конкурентний тиск. Запропоновано стратегічні напрями інноваційно-орієнтованих підприємств щодо підвищення конкурентоспроможності в контексті глобалізації: інвестування в інновації; підвищення ефективності операцій; глобальна присутність; міжнародна кооперація.

Галузь застосування результатів. Конкурентоспроможність підприємства, економіка підприємства, стратегія підприємства, управління підприємствами, інноваційна діяльність підприємства, ефективність діяльності підприємства, міжнародна та глобальна економіка.

Висновки. В результаті нами було доведено, що конкурентоспроможність інноваційно-орієнтованих підприємств у контексті міжнародної глобалізації є складним та багатовимірним явищем, яке потребує ефективної архітекtonіки управління. Встановлено, що підприємства, які здатні адаптуватися до нових викликів, використовуючи інновації як основу своєї стратегії та активного розвитку міжнародну присутність, мають більше шансів на ефективну діяльність. Визначено, що в умовах глобалізації конкурентоспроможність не обмежується лише локальними ринками, вона має міжнародний вимір, що вимагає стратегічного підходу до управління інноваціями та ресурсами. Встановлено, що інтенсивне зростання глобалізації вплинуло на динаміку розвитку багатьох секторів економіки, особливо в умовах поширення інформаційних технологій та швидких інновацій. Доведено, що підприємства інноваційного спрямування, які прагнуть бути конкурентоспроможними на міжнародній арені, повинні постійно адаптуватися до змін та розвивати нові технологічні рішення: конкурентоспроможність таких підприємств багато в чому залежить від їхньої здатності впроваджувати інновації, адаптувати стратегії до глобальних умов і швидко реагувати на нові виклики. Запропоновано визначення архітекtonіки конкурентоспроможності як комплексу взаємопов'язаних компонентів/потенціалів, що дозволяють підприємству зберігати і зміцнювати свої позиції на міжнародних ринках, де інноваційні стратегії, гнучкість та відкритість до змін є основою успішного функціонування в умовах глобальної конкуренції.

Ключові слова: архітекtonіка конкурентоспроможність, інновації, підприємства, міжнародна глобалізація, світовий простір, розвиток підприємств, стратегії, інтеграція, трансформація, потенціал, чинники впливу.

Formulation of the problem. The architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization is gaining relevance in the context of dynamic changes in the world economic space, increasing competition in the global market and the importance of innovation for ensuring the sustainable development of companies. Since companies must be able to quickly adapt to the challenges of globalization, in particular through the introduction of innovative strategies and new technologies, innovation is becoming a key factor in determining the ability of companies not only to maintain their market position but also to expand their capabilities in the international arena.

Today, companies are facing global trends such as digitalization, environmental transformation, and integration into international logistics, which requires an effective competitiveness manage-

ment strategy. The study of competitiveness architectonics allows us to reveal the structural elements and interrelationships that form a comprehensive system of competitive advantages of innovation-oriented enterprises. Given the constant changes in the global market, it is important to understand how globalization processes affect the development of innovative enterprises and what strategies can ensure their sustainability and success in the long run. Thus, the study of this topic is aimed at analyzing the main factors that contribute to the formation of competitive advantages, which is of great importance for the development of modern enterprises seeking to strengthen their positions in the international market in the context of globalization.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The issue of the architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in

the context of international globalization is complex and multifaceted, covering all aspects of global competition, innovation, enterprise management, economics and international business. Among the researchers at the national level, the following should be mentioned: V. Geyets, who studied the issues of economic competitiveness and innovative development; A. Grinev, who studied innovation management and enterprise competitiveness; R. Fakhutdinov, who worked on the issues of competitiveness strategy and innovation management in the context of globalization. Also outstanding are the works of: I. Yermolenko, who specializes in innovation, enterprise development management and strategic management, and S. Kavuna, who studied the strategic development of innovation-oriented enterprises. Among foreign scholars, attention should be paid to the following authors who have studied this issue: M. Porter – one of the most famous researchers of competitive advantages, the developer of the «five forces» model, who researched and studied competitiveness strategies and innovations in the global economy; J. Schumpeter – a researcher of economic development, known for his contribution to the theory of innovation and «creative destruction» as a factor of competitiveness; K. Christensen, who developed the theory of «disruptive innovation», which concerns the impact of innovation on the competitiveness of enterprises; G. Hamel and K. Prahalad, who devoted their works to the concept of strategic resources and competencies that are key to building competitive advantages of innovative enterprises; R. Rumelt, who studied strategic processes and competitiveness, especially in the context of globalization and innovative development. Thus, these authors explore different approaches to the analysis of competitiveness, in particular in the context of globalization, which can be useful for research in this area. However, for the purpose of an in-depth study, we consider it necessary to supplement the topic of the architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization.

Presenting main material. In the context of globalization, modern businesses face new challenges and opportunities that affect their competitiveness. Open markets, the development of information technology and interaction between countries contribute to increased competition. In-

novation-oriented businesses must adapt to new realities to remain competitive in the international market. The competitiveness architecture of innovation-oriented enterprises is becoming an important tool for ensuring their successful operation and growth in the context of international globalization. The competitiveness of an enterprise is the ability to ensure the efficient use of its resources to achieve competitive advantages in the market, where the main components are the quality of products or services, price, level of innovation, marketing strategy, brand reputation, as well as the ability of the enterprise to adapt to changes in the market [1; 4; 7; 12; 15; 18; 23; 27; 29].

Innovations play a key role in increasing the competitiveness of enterprises, especially in the context of globalization, when technological changes and the introduction of new products and processes become the main drivers of economic growth. The competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises is defined as the ability of an enterprise to create innovative products and solutions that are of higher value to consumers than similar products or services of competitors. The architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises includes several key components, each of which plays an important role in building an enterprise development strategy (Fig. 1) [2; 3; 6; 9; 13; 19; 22].

The architectonics of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises is a system of structural and functional components that ensure the enterprise's sustainable market position in the context of the following potentials:

- innovation potential (the ability to generate new ideas and translate them into products or services that are in demand in the market);
- financial potential (the ability to effectively use own and external financial resources to support innovative projects);
- marketing potential (development of a strategy for positioning products on the market, taking into account global trends and peculiarities of international competition);
- organizational potential (building a culture of continuous innovation, cooperation and openness to change).

Each of these potentials plays an important role in ensuring a sustainable competitive position of innovation-oriented enterprises, especially in the context of international globalization [5; 8; 10; 11; 14; 24; 28].

Fig. 1. Composition of components of competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the formation of their development strategy in the context of competitive advantages

Also, the impact of globalization on the competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises should not be underestimated, as it opens up new markets for enterprises, but at the same time increases the level of competition. The growth of international interaction forces companies to increase their requirements for product quality, reduce costs, and introduce innovations.

Companies that cannot adapt to new conditions risk losing their market position. Since globalization creates new opportunities for enterprises and increases the level of competition, certain factors affecting innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of globalization require attention:

- access to international markets – opening up the possibility of entering new markets, which requires the adaptation of products and services to local needs;

- international cooperation – creation of joint projects with other companies or scientific institutions, which allows to increase innovation potential;
- technology transfer – providing opportunities for the rapid introduction of new technologies that require enterprises to invest in research and development;
- competitive pressure – innovation-oriented enterprises are constantly faced with the need to improve product quality, reduce costs and improve services [16; 20; 25; 30].

Since one of the main challenges of globalization is the increasing speed of technological change, where enterprises must constantly invest in research and development to remain at the forefront of the industry and prevent lagging behind competitors, to ensure success in international mar-

Fig. 2. Strategic directions of innovation-oriented enterprises to improve competitiveness in the context of globalization

kets, innovation-oriented enterprises must develop strategies aimed at increasing their competitive advantage (Fig. 2) [13; 15; 17; 21; 26; 30]:

Conclusions

The competitiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of international globalization is a complex and multidimensional phenomenon that requires an effective management architecture. Enterprises that are able to adapt to new challenges, use innovation as the basis of their strategy and actively develop their international presence have a better chance of success. In the context of globalization, competitiveness is not limited to local markets – it has an international dimension, which requires a strategic approach to managing innovations and resources. It is established that the intensive growth of globalization has affected the dynamics of development of many sectors of the economy, especially in the context of the spread of information technology and rapid innovation. Innovative enterprises seeking to be competitive in the international arena must constantly adapt to changes and develop new technological solutions. The competitiveness of such enterprises largely depends on their ability to innovate, adapt

strategies to global conditions and respond quickly to new challenges. In this context, the competitiveness architecture is an important element that combines various aspects of an enterprise's activities. Thus, the effectiveness of innovation-oriented enterprises in the context of globalization depends on the ability to adapt to new challenges and effectively use their innovative capabilities. It is established that the competitiveness architecture includes a set of interrelated components that allow an enterprise to maintain and strengthen its position in international markets, where innovative strategies, flexibility and openness to change are the basis for successful functioning in the context of global competition.

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